

A COMPARISON OF THE THROUGH THICKNESS STRAIN RATE SENSITIVITY OF EGLASS/EPOXY AND EGLASS/LPET UD COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Affordable fibre reinforced lightweight polymer materials are potential candidates to substitute rolled homogenous armour steel in add-on panels for military vehicles [1]. Among other threats, the panels protect against improvised explosive devices (IED), which produce explosions causing high strain rate deformation in both in-plane and out-of-plane directions of the plate as well as shearing. One of the major design decisions is the choice between a thermoset and thermoplastic matrix type where thermoplastic matrix systems are deemed to be favourable due to their higher inherent toughness [2]. The rate sensitivity of the out-of-plane properties for UD fibre laminates has been reported in the literature, but mostly for composite materials with a thermoset (e.g. epoxy) matrix [3-5]. The out-of-plane properties are dominated by the matrix behaviour [2] and an increase in stiffness and fracture stresses were found with increasing strain rate [3-5]. Since the matrix is dominant in the out-of-plane directions, the properties of the fibres have less influence on the rate effects. Thus it is interesting to compare how the strain rate affects the material properties between the two types of matrix materials when fibres are added. This is important with respect to assessing the materials ability to survive an impact and its resilience to multiple hits.

2 Materials

An Eglass/LPET (Thermoplastic) and an Eglass/Epoxy (Thermoset) with unidirectional fibres were tested in the through thickness direction in this setup. Material details are given in in Table 1 with fiber and matrix types.

Specimens were cut with a diamond saw and milled to final dimensions of 12x12x10mm (Width x Height x Thickness) and examples of specimens are shown in Fig. 1.

For the quasi static case the specimen size was 20 x 20 x 40 mm (Width x height x thickness) for stiffness measurements and 25 x 25 x 40mm (W x H x T) with a waisted cross section of 16 x 16mm (W x H).

3 Test setup

The materials were tested in compression under quasi static condition in an Instron 88R1362 servo hydraulic test machine [6, 7] and at 3 different strain rate levels in a split hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB). The strain rate levels were 150, 280 and 430/s for Eglass/LPET and 260, 300 and 490 /s for Eglass/Epoxy. A total of 30 specimens were tested at higher strain rates with 5 specimens for each strain rate and for each material. The specimen dimensions were the same for all three strain rates and the strain rate was varied through pulse shaping and impact speed in the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar.

3.1 The Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar

A modified split hopkinson pressure bar, based at University of Southampton, was used to perform the compression tests at elevated strain rates.

The Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar test rig is well described in the literature [8-10]. For this setup the Incident Bar was made from a high strength stainless steel, 2m long, while the output bar was made from high strength aluminum and only 0.6m long. This is a deviation from the classic setup of the SHPB [8] and this setup was used to recover the specimen after the first initial hit of the Incident Bar. In a classic setup the specimen will be subjected to multiple hits by the Incident bar which prevents post analysis of the specimen in a scanning electron microscope or/and CT scanner, as the damage cannot be considered a result of the measured loading of the specimen alone. The multiple hits occurs as the Reflected wave will travel back and forth in the Incident bar after the initial hit on the specimen and

push the Incident bar forward for each reverberation [10]. The recovery method used in this study is an alternative to the existing methods in the literature which are based on stopping the Incident bar after the first loading [11, 12]. The method used in this study is based on the principle that a Transmission bar with lower density and length than the incident bar will move faster away from the specimen, than the Incident bar will approach the specimen after the initial hit. Data for the Incident bar and Transmitter bar are given in table Table 2.

The Incident bar and Transmitter bar were calibrated by measuring the density and wave speed in the bar. The wave speed was measured by firing the Striker bar on the bars without any specimen and the time between the incident and reflected wave correspond to twice the distance between the strain gage and bar end at the specimen side denoted L_{sg} in Fig. 3. The stiffness can then be calculated as [13]

$$E = C^2 \rho \quad (1)$$

E is the E modulus; C is the one dimensional wave speed and ρ is the density.

The classical formulas for the split hopkinson pressure bar, assume equilibrium across the specimens and are derived with the limitation that the Incident Bar and Transmitter Bar must be of equal diameter and made from the same material [8, 9]. Further the equations also assume no dispersion of the waves as they propagate along the bars. The benefit of keeping identical position of the strain gage is that the signals are automatically time synchronized as both the reflected and transmitted wave will be delayed with the same amount of time from the specimen.

Chen et al. modified the formulas to accommodate bars of different cross-sectional areas but with identical E modulus [14, 15]. However in this case the bar diameter is equal but E modulus is different. In this study a set of equations is derived which can account for both different cross sectional area and E modulus.

The setup is given in Fig. 4 with interface 1 at the Incident Bar/ specimen interface and interface 2 at the specimen/Transmitter bar interface.

The velocity at interface 1 at the onset of reflection can be calculated from the incident wave and the reflected part as [13]

$$V_1(t) = C_I(\varepsilon_I(t) - \varepsilon_R(t)) \quad (2)$$

V_1 is the velocity of the interface between the Incident bar and the specimen; C_I is the wave speed of the Incident bar; ε_I is the Incident wave and ε_R is the reflected wave. The velocity V_2 at the interface between the specimen and the Transmitter bar is solely calculated from the transmitted wave as

$$V_2(t) = C_T \varepsilon_T(t) \quad (3)$$

The strain rate in the specimen can then be calculated from

$$\frac{d\varepsilon}{dt} = \dot{\varepsilon}(t) = \frac{V_1(t) - V_2(t)}{L_s} \quad (4)$$

Where $\dot{\varepsilon}(t)$ is the average strain rate in the specimen and L_s is the specimen length. Inserting (2), (3) into (4) gives

$$\dot{\varepsilon}(t) = \frac{C_I(\varepsilon_I(t) - \varepsilon_R(t)) - C_T \varepsilon_T(t)}{L_s} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) gives the strain rate history and this can be integrated to obtain the strain history of the test as

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{1}{L_s} \int_0^t C_I(\varepsilon_I(\tau) - \varepsilon_R(\tau)) - C_T \varepsilon_T(\tau) d\tau \quad (6)$$

Where $\varepsilon(t)$ is the strain in the specimen. Forces at each end of the specimen can be calculated, using linear elasticity of the bars, as

$$\begin{aligned} P_I(t) &= A_I E_I (\varepsilon_I(t) + \varepsilon_R(t)) \\ P_T(t) &= A_T E_T (\varepsilon_T(t)) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The stress $\sigma_1(t)$ in the specimen at the Incident bar/specimen interface can then be calculated as

$$\sigma_1(t) = \frac{A_I E_I}{A_s} (\varepsilon_I(t) + \varepsilon_R(t)) \quad (8)$$

And the stress $\sigma_2(t)$ in the specimen at the specimen/Transmitter bar interface can be calculated as

$$\sigma_2(t) = \frac{A_T E_T}{A_s} (\varepsilon_T(t)) \quad (9)$$

The average stress $\sigma_s(t)$ in the specimen can be calculated as

$$\sigma_s(t) = \frac{\sigma_1(t) + \sigma_2(t)}{2} \quad (10)$$

Which becomes

$$\sigma_s(t) = \frac{A_I E_I}{2A_s} (\varepsilon_I(\tau) + \varepsilon_R(\tau)) + \frac{A_T E_T}{2A_s} (\varepsilon_T(\tau)) \quad (11)$$

A_I is the cross sectional area of the Incident bar, and E_I is the elastic modulus of the Incident bar. A_T is the cross sectional area of the Incident bar and E_T is the elastic modulus of the Incident bar.

If the specimen is in equilibrium the interface stresses will be equal and the condition in equation (12) will apply.

$$\varepsilon_I + \varepsilon_R = K\varepsilon_T \quad (12)$$

Where K is defined as

$$K = \frac{A_T E_T}{A_I E_I} \quad (13)$$

If $K=1$, i.e. bars of the same material and cross-section, and the equilibrium condition in equation (12) applies, equation (5), (6) and (10) will reduce to

$$\dot{\varepsilon}(t) = \frac{C_I}{L_s} \varepsilon_R(t) \quad (14)$$

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{C_I}{L_s} \int_0^t \varepsilon_R(\tau) d\tau \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_s(t) = \frac{A_I E_I}{A_s} \varepsilon_T(\tau) \quad (16)$$

which are the classic Kolsky formulas [9]. However in this work they are used without the assumption in equation (12) and with K defined as in equation (13). The Incident, reflected and Transmitted wave were time synchronized according to the procedure outlined in [10] and an example of time synchronized signals are given in Fig. 5.

3.2 Pulse shaping

A fast rising Incident pulse will increase the time the specimen needs to attain dynamic equilibrium. The Incident pulse must also be shaped to accommodate different strain rates as the obtained strain rate in the test will be a function of the relative impedances between the bars and specimen and the stress rate of the pulse. The stress rate is a function of the input

speed and the pulse shaping. In this study copper pulse shapers were used and the resistance model in equation (17) of a soft 11000 grade copper were calibrated according to the procedure proposed in [16].

$$\sigma_p = \frac{\sigma_0 \varepsilon_p^n}{1 - \varepsilon_p^m} \quad (17)$$

σ_p is plastic stress in the pulse shaper and ε_p is the plastic strain. The calibrated values were found to be $\sigma_0 = 608,3\text{Mpa}$, $n = 0,2387$, $m = 4,2360$.

From equation (14) it is seen that the strain rate is proportional to the reflected pulse. Taking stress equilibrium at Incident bar/ specimen interface yields

$$\sigma_R(t) = \sigma_s(t) - \sigma_I(t) \quad (18)$$

σ_s is the stress in the specimen σ_R and σ_I is the reflected and Incident stress respectively. The specimens used in this study are elastic up to fracture, so the specimen stress will vary through the test. If σ_R must be constant the Incident pulse must vary with time as σ_s and thus the need for a shaped input pulse to obtain a constant strain rate [10]. Table 3 gives the setup details used for the low, medium and high strain rate regimes.

Fig. 6 shows a copper pulse shaper positioned at the Incident bar and Fig. 8 shows how the input pulse is varied to obtain the strain rate profiles in Fig. 7. To obtain a single strain rate value for each test the strain rate was averages in the strain interval 1-1.8% and the strain rates are shown in Fig. 9 with 95% confidence interval for each strain rate group.

3.3 Dispersion and alignment of pulses

All 3 signals were dispersion corrected by shifting the waves to the Bar/Specimen interface according to the procedure outline in [17, 18] and the relationship between wave speed and wavelength was calculated with the Love approximation of the Pochhammer-Chree wave equation [19].

4 Results

The stress strain curves were generated from the obtained Incident, Reflected and Transmitted pulses using equation (6) and (11). The failure stress was determined as the maximum stress on the stress strain curve and the failure strain was taken as the strain corresponding to the failure stress. The E

modulus was calculated in the interval 1 – 1.8% strain.

Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 shows stress strain curves for the low and high strain rate of the Eglass/LPET material and Fig. 16 shows all the results plotted with 95% confidence interval. The results were grouped in the low, medium and high strain rate groups.

4.1 Digital image correlation check

To verify the measurements, 4 tests (Eglass/Epoxy low strain rate) were conducted with a Vision Research camera V1610 high speed camera to monitor the test. A speckle pattern was painted on the surface of the specimen and The Digital Image Correlation software ARAMIS 2D from GOM [20] was used to calculate the strain field on the surface of the specimen and the strain measurements were taken as an average of the facets within the red square in Fig. 11. The DIC strain measure was used with the stress measure from the SHPB to generate stress strain curves from which the E modulus was calculated. Direct comparisons of the measures are shown in Table 4 and a comparison of stress strain curves are shown in Fig. 9.

A paired T test was conducted with the hypothesis, that the means are equal, were found to be $P = 0.49$, so the means are not significantly different.

5 Discussion

The stress strain curves in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 show a linear response up to fracture for both the low and high strain rates. However the high strain rate results shows more noise in the stress strain curves, but this were due to a noisy Incident wave as shown in Fig. 7. All results are shown in Fig. 16 with failure strain, failure stress and stiffness plotted with 95% confidence interval for each strain rate regime.

Eglass/LPET shows an increase in failure strain and then a drop with increasing strain rate which indicate a change in failure mechanism as the strain rate passes through a strain rate regime. Eglass/Epoxy shows an increase in failure strain from quasi static to the lowest strain rate and then a stable level. Both materials experience an increase in failure stress with strain rate, however the Eglass/LPET is more pronounced to this effect. The Eglass/LPET also shows a higher increase in failure stress from quasi static strain rate to the lower strain compared to the Eglass/Epoxy which indicate a different behavior of the matrix during high strain rate event.

For both materials the stiffness is decreasing with increasing strain rate and behaves softer than under quasi static strain rates.

Some specimens were post analysed by capturing scanning electron images of the fracture surfaces. Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 show the more ductile behavior of the Eglass/LPET in terms of less splitting of the matrix compared to the Eglass/Epoxy. This is contradictory to the behavior in the failure strain plot where the Eglass/Epoxy has higher strain to failure for all strain rates.

6 Conclusion

A thermoset (Eglass/Epoxy) and thermoplastic (Eglass/LPET) fibre reinforced material has been tested for strain rate sensitivity in the thickness direction for a UD layup in a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar. The strain rates ranged from quasi static to 500 /s.

The Eglass/LPET showed a higher sensitivity to strain rate for the failure stress than the Eglass/Epoxy. For failure strain the Eglass/LPET showed an Increase from quasi static strain to 150/s and then slowly decreasing with increasing strain rate. This behavior indicates a shift in failure mode inside the material.

For both materials the E modulus was found to decreasing with increasing strain rate. To check the results from the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar, 4 tests was monitored with Digital Image Correlation and the E modulus was calculated from these results and found similar with the SHPB results.

7 References

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Table 1 - Material details

Property	Eglass/Epoxy	Eglass/LPET
Panel size	200x200x21,9mm	250x250x22mm
Fabrics	Non crimp fabric SAERTEX S14EU990-00940- T1300-499000 With 950g/m2	E-glass 1200 tex 4588 WG2-LPET-1000- UD With 1050g/m2
Area weight	43,4kg/m2	
Layup	[0°] ₃₆	[0°] ₄₄
Matrix	Araldite LY 564 Epoxy with Aradur 917 harder and DY 070 accelerator	LPET
Production method	Vacuum Infusion	Vacuum consolidation

Table 2 Bar Properties

	Incident bar	Transmitter bar
Material	Stainless steel	Alu 7075 T651
Length (m)	2.001	0.617
E modulus E (GPa)	191.9	73.4
Density ρ (kg/m ³)	7741	2809
Wave speed C (m/s)	4978	5112

Table 3 - Pulseshaping setup

	Low Strain rate	Medium strain rate	High Strain rate
Copper Pulse shaper dimension (Dia. x Thk)	8,73 x 2mm	9,53 x 2mm	11,41 x 2mm
Strikerbar length (mm)	150	150	100

Table 4 - Comparison of calculated stiffness for SHPB and DIC measurements

Specimen	SHPB analysis E modulus (GPa)	DIC Analysis E modulus (GPa)
01	7.54	7.83
02	9.34	9.83
03	9.66	8.85
04	8.65	7.33

Fig. 1 – Eglass/LPET specimens.

Fig. 2 - The modified Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar

Fig. 3 - Travel distance between the Incident and Reflected wave

Fig. 4 Schematic overview of the specimen, bar interfaces. The interface between the Incident bar and the specimen is numbered 1, while the interface between the specimen and the Transmitter bar is numbered 2

Fig. 5 - Time synchronized signals

Fig. 6 - Copper pulse shaper positioned on the Incident Bar

Fig. 7 - Incident pulses for different strain rates

Fig. 8 - Three levels of strain rates

Fig. 9 - Obtained strain rates

Fig. 10 - Comparison of stress strain curves generated with SHPB and DIC as strain measure

Fig. 11 – Digital Image Correlation measurements

Fig. 12 - Eglass/LPET

Fig. 13 - Eglass/Epoxy

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Fig. 14 – CRBB22E-01-05

Fig. 15 CRBB22E-11-15

Fig. 16 - Failure strain, failure stress and E modulus plotted with 95% confidence interval